

ISic1525

I.Sicily inscription 1525

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15512

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀρτεμισίαλ Εὐ
2. τύχης ἡγόρ[ε]σαι
3. ἰδίᾳ κλητρί τύμ
4. βον ἔβδομ[ή]κον τα δύων μυριά δων ὀπόθεν αὐ
7. τῆ κεῖταλι ὤδαι

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1896

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645025

Bibliography

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Orsi, P. 1896. Gli scavi a S. Giovanni a Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 10: 1-59. At 81
Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 209 n.1

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